

**Office of Human Subjects Research
Institutional Review Boards**

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Date: January 21, 2025

PROGRESS REPORT ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Review Type: Expedited
Principal Investigator: Christopher Chute
Number: PR00005914 / IRB00249128
Title: National COVID Cohort Collaborative (N3C): A national resource for shared analytics
Committee Chair: Richard Moore
IRB Committee: IRB-3

Date of acknowledgement: January 21, 2025

Date of expiration: January 21, 2027

JHM IRB is serving as the Single IRB for this study. Continuing Review approval applies to the following participating sites:

- Loyola University Chicago
- Tulane University
- University Of Cincinnati
- LSU's Pennington Biomedical Research Center
- University Hospitals Cleveland Medical Center
- University of New Mexico Health Sciences Center
- University Of Iowa
- Ochsner Clinic Foundation
- University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
- University Of Miami
- Oregon Health & Science University
- University of Southern California - Health Science Campus
- Mayo Clinic
- Northwestern University Feinberg School of Medicine

- Medical College of Wisconsin
- University Of Kentucky
- Louisiana State University Health Science Center New Orleans
- University of Texas Houston Health Science Center
- University of Washington
- University Of Illinois At Chicago
- University of Utah
- NewYork-Presbyterian Queens
- Duke University Health System, Inc.
- University of Rochester
- University Of Chicago
- University of Colorado Denver
- University of Arkansas for Medical Sciences
- Washington University in St. Louis
- OCHIN, Inc
- Arkansas Children's Research Institute
- University Of Mississippi Medical Center
- Emory University
- Carilion Clinic
- The Nemours Foundation
- University Medical Center of Southern Nevada
- University of Wisconsin-Madison
- MetroHealth System
- Vanderbilt University Medical Center
- The Queen's Medical Center
- University Of Virginia
- University of Minnesota
- University Of Nebraska Medical Center
- Ohio State University
- Wake Forest University Health Sciences
- George Washington University
- Stanford University
- University Of Kansas Medical Center
- Children's National Medical Center
- Weill Cornell Medical College
- CAMC Health Education and Research Institute, Inc.
- University of Puerto Rico Medical Sciences Campus
- University Of Michigan
- SUNY Stony Brook
- Baylor College Of Medicine
- University of Texas Health Science Center at San Antonio
- Medical University of South Carolina
- University Medical Center New Orleans
- Indiana University
- University of Massachusetts Medical School
- University Of Texas Medical Branch, Galveston
- Virginia Commonwealth University
- University Of Oklahoma Health Sciences Center
- MaineHealth

The above-referenced participating sites should be provided a copy of the continuing review approval letter.

- Study is a Secondary Use of Data or Specimens Only.

Documents approved as part of this Progress Report Includes:

- A Johns Hopkins pSite Continuing Review Summary Sheet
- pSite Continuing Review Summary Sheets for other participating sites

IRB review included the following:

45 CFR 46.116: A waiver of consent was granted based on the following criteria: 1) the research involves no more than minimal risk to subjects; 2) the waiver will not adversely affect the rights and welfare of the subjects; 3) the research could not be practicably carried out without the waiver; and 4) the IRB will advise you if it is appropriate for participants to be provided with additional pertinent information after participation.

The IRB has made the seven findings required under 45 CFR 46.305(a).

If this study is a clinical trial and data collection is complete for the prespecified primary outcome, Section 801 of the Food and Drug Administration Amendments Act requires reporting of summary results information at <http://www.clinicaltrials.gov>. Reporting must be done within 12 months of completing data collection for the prespecified primary outcome, regardless of sponsor or funding source. Failure to comply with this law may result in civil penalties. For more information on results reporting go to <http://www.clinicaltrials.gov>. If the study is registered with Clinicaltrials.gov and is closed to recruitment and enrollment, the record must be updated within 30 days to reflect the study's enrollment status. See <http://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/manage-recs/how-edit> for more information. Questions can be directed to register@clinicaltrials.gov.

Expiration Date: The expiration date for this research is listed above. If a continuing review application is required for this research and the approval lapses, the research must stop and you must submit a request to the IRB to determine whether it is in the best interests of individual participants to continue with protocol-related procedures.

Changes in Research: All proposed changes to the research must be submitted using a Change in Research application. The changes must be approved by the JHM IRB prior to implementation, with the following exception: changes made to eliminate apparent immediate hazards to participants may be made immediately, and promptly reported to the JHM IRB.

Continuing Review/Progress Report: Continuing Review/Progress Report Applications should be submitted at least 6 weeks prior to the study expiration date.

If a progress report is required, failure to submit a progress report in the time period requested will result in your inability to submit any further study actions other than a progress report until your progress report is submitted and acknowledged.

If a Continuing Review application is required, failure to allow sufficient time for review may result in a lapse of approval. If the Continuing Review Application is not submitted prior to the expiration date, your study will be terminated and a New Application must be submitted to reinitiate the research.

Unanticipated Problems: All unanticipated problems must be submitted using a Protocol Event Report.

If this research has a commercial sponsor, the research may not start until the sponsor and JHU have signed a contract.

The Johns Hopkins Institutions operate under multiple Federal-Wide Assurances: The Johns Hopkins University School of Medicine - FWA00005752, Johns Hopkins Health System and Johns Hopkins Hospital - FWA00006087